

Graph of Coronavirus Daily New Cases and Other Charts about Tests, Effective Reproduction Rate, Stringency Index and Variants for Italy

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Dipartimento di Scienza Applicata e Tecnologia, Politecnico di Torino, Torino, Italia

The web site worldometer, <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>, is giving data about Covid-19 Coronavirus Pandemic. For each country, the site is showing, among several charts, those of the daily new cases, from February 15, 2020, to the day of the visualization of the page (in this work, the beginning of October, 2021). A 7-day moving average is also displayed for data. Here we show the chart and the recurrence plot of such averaged daily new cases, concerning Italy. We will consider also data charts from the web site Our World in Data, <https://ourworldindata.org/>, given according to 7-day moving average too. Data are concerning the daily number of tests, the percentage tests being positive for the virus, the effective reproduction rate and the stringency index. From the percentage of positive tests, a discussion about the circulation of the virus during the first wave in Italy is proposed and an estimate of the daily new cases at its peak. Among the several data analysed by Our World in Data, <https://ourworldindata.org/>, we can find also the percentage of variants circulating in each country. The charts for daily new cases, stringency index and vaccinated people will be given also for the United Kingdom, in the framework of a discussion made by Giorgio Parisi, Nobel Laureate 2021 in Physics.

Keywords: Covid-19, Coronavirus Pandemic, Recurrence Plots, Daily New Cases, Daily Number of Tests, Positive Percentage, Reproduction Rate, Stringency Index, Variants.

Torino, 7 October 2021

The web site worldometer, <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>, is giving data about Covid-19 Coronavirus Pandemic. For each country, the site is showing, among several graphs, those of the daily new cases, from February 15, 2020, to the day of the visualization of the page (here, it is at beginning of October 2021).

Actually all these data can be considered as time series. These series are commonly used in signal processing [1]. They are consisting of sequences of data measured typically at successive points, which are spaced at uniform time intervals. Time series can be analysed using frequency-domain and time-domain methods: the former includes spectral analysis, the latter autocorrelation and cross-correlation analysis. Among the methods based on the time-domain, we find the recurrence plots. These plots are displaying the recurrence of states of the dynamical system, that is, states that are arbitrarily close again after some time of divergence [2,3]. Therefore, the plot is based on the datum observed at time i and its recurrence at a different time j , depicted within a two-dimensional squared black and white image, with black dots marking recurrences. Both axes of the image were time axes. The resulting image was depending on a threshold distance, which was determining the nearer states in the phase space. It is also possible to investigate cross-recurrences [4].

Nowadays, several tools are freely available to have the recurrence plots from data files, using colours and different layouts to represent distances between the states. Here, we will use the tool developed by E. Kononov, www.visualization-2002.org/ [5].

Daily New Cases

Cases per Day
Data as of 0:00 GMT+0

Data courtesy <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/country/italy/>

In the following, the recurrence plot of daily new cases for Italy is given, from February 15, 2020, to the day of the visualization of the page (in this work, October 2, 2021), with a 7-day moving average.

ITALY (Daily New Cases)

Let us note that the number of confirmed cases is lower than the actual number of cases.

Recurrence plots (on the left) for coronavirus daily new cases from worldometer, 7-days average. On the two axes we have the days of observations (from February 15, 2020, to October 2, 2021). The data given in white colour are representing the largest variation of the counts. Black and dark grey are representing small variations and therefore a recurrence. Therefore, the recurrence is evidenced by dark pixels, as in the case of the original proposal by Eckmann, Kamphorst and

Ruelle, 1987. The plot given above has been obtained using the Grey Scheme, with inverted tones, of the tool “Visual Recurrence” Analysis, developed by E. Kononov, www.visualization-2002.org/. The tool is also allowing to plot data.

In the recurrence plot, we can see curved patterns linked to the peak of the first wave (40) and, in a small part of it, to the peak of the last (fourth) wave (550). To have the end of the last wave, in the case of no further waves, an interval of about fifty days is necessary. The largest peak (second wave) is at 273 (November 15, 2020), and the peak of the third wave at 395 (March 19, 2021): also in these case we observe a curved pattern.

In the case we had a single peak, the recurrence plot, in grey scale, would be like the following one, where the curved pattern (bow and arrow) is marked by red pixels.

Waves

In [6], we can find told that “The World Health Organization and other international health organizations often refer to "waves" of a pandemic, but no formal definition exists. A wave refers to a rising number of COVID-19 cases that has a specific peak and then declines. On a graph it looks similar to the shape of a wave that increases, tops out, then decreases. A wave can also be referred to in some cases as a surge or outbreak”. In fact, from the recurrence plots given before, we can see that a “wave” can be the convolution of two or more peaks.

Ref. 6 continues telling that “Public health scientists first began using this term [wave] to describe different peaks and valleys of infections during influenza outbreaks in the late 1800s and the 1918-1929 Spanish flu.” The Reference is also stressing that each “wave” has a different feature and can impact different populations, even within the same country. “The first wave of an epidemic means that that virus starts spreading among many people, more and more each day, and then a peak number of daily cases is reached. ... After that peak, the virus spreads less as more people have either been infected or have learned how to prevent themselves from getting infected or spreading the virus, so rates of transmission get lower and fewer people are getting sick over that period of time”. In Italy, on 9 March 2020, the government, Prime Minister Giuseppe Conte, imposed a national lockdown, restricting the movement of the population except for necessity, work, and health circumstances.

In the recurrence plot and chart given above, we can see that the “first wave” was from March to June 2020. The “second wave” started in October 2020. Being the following data showing a

convolution of at least two other peaks, let us assume the end of the “third wave” in June 2021. Some web sites, such as Wikipedia, for instance, define the peak about March 2021 as the “third wave” (it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gestione_della_pandemia_di_COVID-19_in_Italia#Terza_ondata). However, the virus was largely circulating before March 2021.

In the following, we will consider also charts from the web site Our World in Data, <https://ourworldindata.org/>, given according to 7-day moving average too. Data are concerning the daily number of tests, the percentage tests being positive for the virus, the effective reproduction rate and the stringency index. From the percentage of positive tests, an estimate of the coronavirus daily new cases during the first wave in Italy is proposed. Among the several data analysed by Our World in Data, <https://ourworldindata.org/>, we can find also the percentage of variants circulating in each country.

ITALY

Number of daily tests made in Italy are available at the web site of Our World in Data, <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/full-list-covid-19-tests-per-day?country=~ITA> – Many thanks to this site for the following plot.

Tests

For the discussion of the waves, let us consider the number of tests too. For instance, let us examine the peak of the first wave. It is low, when compared to those of the second wave. A reason was in a limited number of people tested in that period.

From https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_testing#History - “In January 2020, scientists from China published the first genetic sequences of SARS-CoV-2 via GISAID, a program that normally handled genetic sequence data. Researchers around the world used that data to build molecular tests for the virus. Antigen- and antibody-based tests were developed later. Even once the first tests were created, the supply was limited. As a result, no countries had reliable data on the prevalence of the

virus early in the pandemic. ... Shortages of reagent and other testing supplies became a bottleneck for mass testing in the EU, the UK and the US. Early tests also encountered problems with reliability” (see also the given references)”.

We can find the number of daily tests made in Italy at the web site of Our World in Data, <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/full-list-covid-19-tests-per-day?country=~ITA> , as given previously. Let us note that the number of tests is different from the number of people tested. A person could have been subjected to more that one test in a day. The chart is clearly showing that the value of the daily new cases of the first wave was based on a low number of daily tests. In the case of the second wave and third wave, we can see that between the two peaks, November 15, 2020, and March 19, 2021, the number of tests and people tested decreased. And the peak of March 18, 2021, is based on a quite larger number of tests. Sadly, the peaks of second and third wave are not an artificial result of an increased number of tests, because large numbers of daily victims of the virus had been reported for first, second and third wave.

Actually, during the first wave, the number of daily new cases was largely underestimated. We can add another plot from Our World in Data. From it, we have the percentage of tests positive for the virus in Italy.

Comparing the percentage of positive tests at the peak of the second wave and the peak of the last wave, we find a ratio of $16/3 = 5.333$. Multiplying the value of the daily new cases for the last peak, about 6500, by factor 5.333, we find a value of 35600, and 35000 circa was the number of new cases at the peak of the second wave, given by www.worldometers.info/ . In the case of second and third peak, the ratio is $16 / 7.5 = 2.1$; multiplying by this factor the daily new cases of the third wave, about 22500, we find 48000 instead of 35000.

The circulation of the virus in Italy during the first wave was constrained differently from that of the second, third and the last wave, which is strongly affected by vaccines. Assuming the percentage of positive tests as related to the circulation of the virus, we could use the ratio of percentages to give some roughly estimate for the new daily cases at the peak of the first wave. Using the second peak, we have $35000 \times 27/16 = 59000$. Using the third peak, $22500 \times 27 / 7.5 = 81000$. The last peak gives $6500 \times 27 / 3 = 58500$. Accordingly, the number of daily new cases was at least ten time larger, at the peak of the first wave, of the number (5600) reported by www.worldometers.info/ .

The last “wave” in Italy, that is the pandemic after July 2021, is strongly influenced by vaccines.

Only one dose is administered to people that had COVID.

COVID-19 vaccine doses administered per 100 people

Source: Official data collated by Our World in Data - Last updated 1 October 2021, 10:40 (London time)
OurWorldInData.org/coronavirus • CC BY

Reproduction rate

Let us consider another chart from Our World Data. It is concerning the reproduction rate, which represents the average number of new infections caused by a single infected individual. If the rate is greater than 1, the infection is able to spread in the population. If it is below 1, the number of cases occurring in the population will gradually decrease to zero.

Estimate of the effective reproduction rate (R) of COVID-19

The reproduction rate represents the average number of new infections caused by a single infected individual. If the rate is greater than 1, the infection is able to spread in the population. If it is below 1, the number of cases occurring in the population will gradually decrease to zero.

Source: Arroyo-Marioli F, Bullano F, Kucinskas S, Rondón-Moreno C (2021) Tracking R of COVID-19: A new real-time estimation using the Kalman filter.
CC BY

Stringency index

Let us continue reading [6]. In this references it is stressed that, during the second wave, “Often treatments and vaccines start to be tested during this period of time because scientists hopefully know more about the virus, its genetics, how it spreads, and what other impacts on the body it has during this time. During the second wave doctors are typically able to diagnose the illness more easily”. Governments are also assuming different restrictions to contain the spread of the virus.

About restrictions, a stringency index has been proposed by [7], authors Hannah Ritchie, Edouard Mathieu, Lucas Rodés-Guirao, Cameron Appel, Charlie Giattino, Esteban Ortiz-Ospina, Joe Hasell, Bobbie Macdonald, Diana Beltekian and Max Roser (2020). As told in [7], the Stringency Index is “a composite measure based on nine response indicators, rescaled to a value from 0 to 100 (100 = strictest). “The nine metrics used to calculate the Stringency Index are: school closures; workplace closures; cancellation of public events; restrictions on public gatherings; closures of public transport; stay-at-home requirements; public information campaigns; restrictions on internal movements; and international travel controls”.

Authors tell that “It’s important to note that this index simply records the strictness of government policies. It does not measure or imply the appropriateness or effectiveness of a country’s response. A higher score does not necessarily mean that a country’s response is ‘better’ than others lower on the index”.

SARS-CoV-2 sequences by variant

Our World
in Data

The share of analyzed sequences in the last two weeks that correspond to each variant group. This share may not reflect the complete breakdown of cases since only a fraction of all cases are sequenced.

Discussione

La figura precedente mostra la circolazione delle varianti in Italia. Il virus originariamente circolante in Italia è rappresentato in grigio. A inizio Gennaio 2021, la variante Inglese rappresentava il 20% circa dei casi. Ad inizio Febbraio era il 60%.

A questo punto è interessante riportare quanto disse Giorgio Parisi, Nobel per la Fisica 2021, il 2 Marzo durante un'intervista al Corriere della Sera, riguardo la terza ed una possibile quarta ondata, guidata dall'emergere di una nuova variante del virus, cosa che poi è puntualmente accaduta.

https://www.corriere.it/cronache/21_marzo_02/covid-terza-ondata-piu-contagiosa-letale-prepariamoci-quarta-0c1a05b2-7b23-11eb-a9cc-1eebe11a6a7c.shtml

Ecco alcuni estratti.

Professore, questa allora è la terza ondata? «A dire il vero la seconda non è finita, quindi si può

discutere se si tratti di una recrudescenza di quella o di una fase successiva. In ogni caso ha senso chiamarla terza ondata perché ha caratteristiche diverse: le varianti».

Di cosa stiamo parlando? «La mutazione inglese per esempio ha una contagiosità superiore del 50% e una letalità più alta del 30%. Mantenendo le misure costanti i casi raddoppierebbero in poco meno di due settimane».

Quando ha iniziato a pensare alla nuova ondata? «Dal momento che non arrivavano segnalazioni di variante inglese pensavo in Italia fosse attorno al 2-3% dei nuovi casi. Ma quando l'Istituto superiore di sanità a inizio febbraio ha detto che era al 18% quello è stato il segnale». [Probabile che il dato sia quello di Gennaio, comunicato a Febbraio dall'Istituto di Sanità]

Parlava di quarta ondata... «Se dovessero spuntare nuove varianti che sfuggono ai vaccini attuali è necessaria una campagna vaccinale di richiamo a dicembre-gennaio. Ma bisogna pensarla ora».

Come aveva segnalato Parisi, l'arrivo di una nuova variante, la Delta, ha portato ad una nuova ondata, mitigata in Italia dai vaccini.

A Luglio 2021 è cominciata la quarta ondata. Oggi, l'unica variante circolante in Italia è la Delta.

Successivamente, il 4 Marzo 2021, Giorgio Parisi è intervenuto in una trasmissione televisiva, di cui uno stralcio è disponibile nel seguente video: <https://youtu.be/n3Xjs1sxqmw>

In questo video, Parisi si riferisce ai dati provenienti dal Regno Unito, affermando che le misure restrittive imposte dal governo hanno influenzato più della campagna vaccinale sulla circolazione del virus. Il Fatto Quotidiano riporta (5 Ottobre 2021) sulla discussione tra Giorgio Parisi e Matteo Bassetti.

“Era il 4 marzo 2021 e Giorgio Parisi, oggi insignito del premio Nobel della Fisica assieme a Syukuro Manabe e a Klaus Hasselmann, fu protagonista di una vivace polemica con l’infettivologo Matteo Bassetti, nel corso della trasmissione “L’aria che tira” (La7). Lo scienziato spiegò che il calo dei contagi in Inghilterra era dovuto, in primis, alle misure restrittive e al lockdown e in seconda analisi ai vaccini, suscitando il dissenso di Bassetti, che pochi minuti prima aveva duramente criticato la campagna vaccinale in Italia”. ... Il fisico sottolineò: “Io so leggere i dati, anzi la mia specialità è leggere i dati. E i dati inglesi dicono una cosa chiarissima, che è l’opposta di quello che ha detto il dottor Bassetti: la diminuzione enorme dei casi è cominciata prima della campagna vaccinale, che non poteva produrre da sola quel calo. La diminuzione di casi è dovuta al lockdown strettissimo che è stato fatto. Adesso sicuramente la campagna vaccinale può aiutare ed aiuterà moltissimo per la diminuzione di casi”. Parisi aggiunse che la campagna vaccinale italiana, ferocemente criticata da Bassetti, non si discostava molto da quella tedesca.

Mostriamo allora i dati di confronto.

Il picco, nel Regno Unito (terza ondata) è stato raggiunto a Gennaio, esattamente l’otto Gennaio 2021. Come si vede dal grafico seguente, il 5 Gennaio, lo Stringency Index ha raggiunto il suo valore massimo per il Regno Unito. Il numero di casi si dimezza (420) a fine Gennaio.

Al 5 Gennaio del 2021, solo il 2% della popolazione del Regno Unito aveva ricevuto una dose di vaccino. Il 26 Gennaio era il 10% ed il 5 Febbraio era il 16 %. Quando il valore del picco si è dimezzato, poco più del 10% della popolazione aveva ricevuto una dose di vaccino.

I dati su lockdown e vaccini sono congruenti con quanto affermato a Marzo da Giorgio Parisi.

Dopo l'assegnazione del Nobel a Parisi, arriva un commento https://www.adnkronos.com/nobel-parisi-bassetti-complimenti-ma-su-dati-covid-avevo-ragione-io_r7k2wII2qJiSVu9K3pFqp

"Il neo premio Nobel per la Fisica sosteneva, ricorda Bassetti, "che in Inghilterra si fossero ridotti il numero dei morti e i casi grazie al lockdown. Io gli dicevo 'guarda che non è così ma è grazie ai vaccini' e mi pare che quello che è successo nei sei mesi successivi - rivendica - dia ragione più a Bassetti [dice Bassetti] che è un medico che a Parisi che è un fisico". Ed ancora "Sul fatto che lui sappia leggere i dati - chiarisce Bassetti tornando su una delle affermazioni fatte da Parisi in quel confronto tv - nessuno ha dubbi ma il fatto che l'epidemia in Inghilterra sia stata controllata dal lockdown è un'inesattezza scientifica. Io mi sono fatto una risata su Parisi ma anche oggi - afferma l'infettivologo - se mi dicesse la stessa cosa, seppure da Nobel della Fisica, riderei. E come ho detto ad altri premi Nobel che sbagliavano lo direi anche a lui".

Se si discute delle parole di Parisi, ci si deve riferire ai dati precedenti Marzo 2021. Quello che è successo nei sei mesi successivi non riguarda le affermazioni del fisico.

References

1. G. Box and G. Jenkins, Time Series Analysis Forecasting and Control, Holden-Day, San Francisco, 1976.
2. J.-P. Eckmann, S.O. Kamphorst and D. Ruelle, Recurrence Plots of Dynamical Systems, Europhysics Letters, 1987, Volume 5, Pages 973-977.
3. J.-P. Eckmann and D. Ruelle, Ergodic Theory of Chaos and Strange Attractors, Review of Modern Physics, 1985, Volume 57, Issue 3, Pages 617-656.
4. A.C. Sparavigna, Recurrence Plots of Sunspots, Solar Flux and Irradiance, arXiv:0804.1941 [physics.pop-ph], 2008
5. E. Kononov, Visual Recurrence Analysis, www.visualization-2002.org/
6. <https://health-desk.org/articles/what-are-first-second-and-third-waves-of-infections>
7. Hannah Ritchie, Edouard Mathieu, Lucas Rodés-Guirao, Cameron Appel, Charlie Giattino, Esteban Ortiz-Ospina, Joe Hasell, Bobbie Macdonald, Diana Beltekian and Max Roser (2020) - "Coronavirus Pandemic (COVID-19)". Published online at OurWorldInData.org. Retrieved from: '<https://ourworldindata.org/coronavirus>' [Online Resource]